

Substance Use Disorders among Patients With Sickle Cell Disease, A Case Series and Literature Review

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Abstract

Introduction

The commonest complication of sickle cell disease (SCD) is vaso-occlusive crises resulting in recurrent pain episodes. The stress of adult roles and responsibilities increases this risk as well as the use of substances to relieve pain and reduce stress. This increases their chances of developing substance use disorders. This study aimed at reawakening clinicians to the increasing problem of drug abuse among SCD patients.

Methods.

This case series and literature review employed a qualitative and quantitative study design involving 8 SCD patients attending a mental health clinic. Diagnoses of Substance use disorders and mental disorders was based on ICD 11 diagnostic criteria. Qualitative data analysis was triangulated with quantitative data analyzed using SPSS version 25 for continuous and categorical variables.

Results: Mean age of participants was 34.57(SD± 5.79). Types of substances used included: pentazocine, amphetamine, ketamine, and cannabis. Pentazocine was the commonest, followed by cannabis. Reasons for substance use include pain, cravings, withdrawal symptoms, insomnia, loss of appetite, and for relaxation. Three (37.5%) of the patients inject selves. Complications reported included, dirty wounds, ulcers, abscesses, ugly scars/swellings and priapism. At least 62.5 % of the clients had co-morbid substance use disorder (SUD) and mental illness e.g. depression, anxiety, insomnia, suicidal ideation and aggressive tendencies.

Conclusion: Substance use disorders is common among SCD patients, often unrecognized and frequently co-morbid with mental disorders emphasizing the importance of a holistic and multidisciplinary approach in the management of adults with sickle cell disease.

Introduction:

Sickle cell disease (SCD) is one of the hemoglobinopathies, a hereditary disorder of hemoglobin (the oxygen carrying pigment in red blood cells).^{1,2} Persons with SCD experience painful crises as one of their commonest symptoms. Painful symptoms often result from vaso-occlusion (blood vessel clogging) by non-pliable sickle red blood cells when they undergo deoxygenation at the tissue level.¹

Even though the incidence of SCD has been largely stable, the prevalence has been increasing as the number of people born with SCD has increased globally and particularly so in the Latin America, the Caribbean, and Central and Sub-Saharan Africa, with an estimated increase from 453000 to 515000 between 2000 and 2021— a 13.7% increase (95% CI: 11.1–16.5). This has given rise to a global sickle cell disease birth rate of 382 (95% CI: 316–456) per 100,000 live births.³⁻⁵

These regional increases in the prevalence of the disease have been attributed to population increase and better health services in some parts of the world resulting in increased socioeconomic, physical and psychological burden of the disease.³⁻⁵

With advances in medicine and pharmacotherapy, under-five mortality among SCD patients have significantly reduced with patients now growing into adulthood and undertaking various adult roles in society including family-hood. These increased roles and responsibilities

also increase their risk for painful crises from various environmental exposures such as cold weather, high altitude, infections/infestations and physical and psychological stressors;^{1,6,7} putting them at increased need for analgesia which in turn increases their risks for substance abuse and dependence.⁸ This is in recognition and contextualization of the increasing availability of substances of abuse and prevalence of substance use, and/or substance use disorders in the general population.⁹

Substance use disorders among the general population continue to be high worldwide. In 2021, one in every 17 people aged 15–64 in the world had used a drug in the past 12 months. Users are estimated to have grown from 240 million in 2011 to 296 million in 2021 (5.8 per cent of the global population aged 15–64); a 23 per cent increase.⁹ In Nigeria, drug use prevalence has tripled global estimates (15% vs 5.5%), and much so among young persons^{10,11}

One of the cornerstones in the management of pain among SCD patients is the use of analgesics which has also undergone variations, sophistication and potency over the decades.¹⁻³ Mild to moderate pains are managed with simple analgesics such as paracetamol and Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs). More severe and chronic pain crises are managed with more potent analgesics such as Opioids in a controlled manner.¹² Patient-controlled analgesia systems using

intravenous opiate administration has become the norm in many climes, giving better results in pain relief.²

Despite the effectiveness of analgesia in the management of pain crises in SCD, there is increasing awareness of the thin line between chronic pain management and opioid dependency syndrome among patients with sickle cell disease.^{12,13} Opioids through their action at the mu receptors, facilitate pain relief but also cause euphoria and pleasure as well as reduction in anxiety levels (through mood alteration). However, tolerance for opioids develop from chronic and increasing use when the mu receptors are internalized by their cells in response to high doses of exogenous opioids resulting in down-regulation of second messenger systems that are mediating the activities of the receptors. All these activities result in obnoxious withdrawal symptoms such as diarrhoea, diaphoresis, insomnia, restlessness, cramps, craving, etc.^{14,15} These are the antecedents that precede drug seeking behaviour and all subsequent attendant consequences.

Current medical ethics emphasize the need for abolishing pain completely or at least, mitigating its impact significantly. While acute pain is relatively straight forward in its management, chronic pain can become complicated, sometimes creating confusion on how much medication is enough, whether the experienced pain is tissue based, and when has abuse of medication set in?^{12,13} Studies now show that chronic pain has a bidirectional relationship with psychological distress and mental disorders such as anxiety disorders, depression, insomnia, somatization,

cognitive impairment, etc. Conversely, chronic pain, when left untreated can become more complex and complicated beyond its original cause, resulting in structural and functional alterations in the nervous system such that pain ceases to be symptomatic of the initial cause but becomes an entirely distinct condition on its own.¹⁶⁻¹⁸ Psychological stressors (a common occurrence among SCD patients) are known to cause microvascular vasoconstriction which further increases the chances for vaso-occlusion and pain crises.¹⁹

Chronic pain and mental disorders

Pain, traditionally described as a noxious/unpleasant stimulus is defined by the International Association for the Study of Pain (IASP), as an unpleasant subjective and emotional experience associated with tissue damage or potential tissue damage.¹⁷

Pain can be mechanical, chemical and thermal, and is classified as Acute, or chronic. Chronic pain has been defined by the American Pain Society and the IASP as pain that “persists beyond the normal tissue healing time, which is assumed to be 3 months”.²⁰ Pain can also be mild, moderate or severe in intensity.

Studies have found relationships between chronic pain and mental disorders such as depression, anxiety, insomnia, cognitive impairment, sexual disorders, suicide, and substance use disorder.^{6,7,16,17}

Several medical conditions present with chronic pain; these include cancers (and their treatment), degenerative spine disease, osteoarthritis, fibromyalgia, human immunodeficiency virus, migraine,

diabetic neuropathy, postherpetic neuralgia etc.

Chronic pain is now recognized to cause both structural and functional alterations in the nervous system resulting in both physical and psychological consequences for patients. This has been supported by research using functional imaging which suggests that mental health disorders and chronic pain share biological mechanisms. This inter-connectivity is exemplified in the finding that depression and anxiety can make their victims more sensitive to pain.¹⁶⁻¹⁸

People living with chronic pain are at heightened risk for mental health problems than those without chronic pain.¹⁶ Bondesson et al. in a prospective cohort study followed up 504,365 subjects within a Sweden population with no initial pain or mental health conditions, for over a decade. They recruited inpatients and outpatients from both primary and specialized care settings. They found an incident rate ratio (IRR) of 2.18 (95% CI = 2.14 - 2.22) for developing a mental illness following a pain condition; and an IRR of 2.02 (95% CI = 1.98 - 2.06) for developing pain after a mental illness.²¹

An estimated 35% to 45% of people with chronic pain experience depression. The Anxiety and Depression Association of America (ADAA) maintain that pain is a common symptom among people with an anxiety disorder, particularly generalized anxiety disorder. Anxiety, depression, and other mood disorders commonly occur at the same time as chronic pain from other painful conditions like fibromyalgia, back aches, migraines and arthritis.²²

In another study, the Mental Health America used data from its online mental health screening program to analyse the intersection between mental health and chronic pain. More than 160,000 individuals who were screened using the Mental Health America Screening Program were found to be living with arthritis or other chronic pain within a 10 year period. Participants with chronic pain were more likely to have several mental health conditions, including severe anxiety, depression, bipolar and PTSD. For example, 47% of those with chronic pain screened positive for severe depression compared to 36% of those without chronic pain.²³

The brain is not designed to handle pain all day. When it does, it takes away the processing power from other brain areas to compensate, and this can change the structure of grey matter. Studies show that chronic pain patients can lose up to 11% of grey matter (areas of the brain that control learning, attention, memory processing, and motor control) as opposed to those without chronic pain. The more prolonged chronic pain persists, the more grey matter is altered and explains why patients with chronic pain have memory loss, attention deficits, decline in problem-solving abilities, and motor control issues, even in areas unaffected by the pain.^{24,25}

Insomnia is one of the most common complications of chronic pain, with over 50% of patients experiencing it at some point. Additionally, insomnia can result in fatigue, mood disorders, and difficulty with concentration and memory as well as exacerbate the existing sleep disturbance.^{25,26}

Research also shows that subjects experiencing chronic pain undergo hormonal deregulation resulting in symptoms such as hot flashes, reduced muscle mass, and lower sex drive and trouble with emotional intimacy.²⁵

Unfortunately, existing healthcare services and specialists to manage several chronic pain conditions are severely insufficient in low- and middle-income countries (LMIC). In developed countries, pain remains a significant issue, with as many as 30% of patients misusing opioids and an alarming surge in drug overdose deaths.¹⁷

Relationship Between chronic pain and Substance use/use disorders

The desire to avoid pain (either physical or emotional) has long been one of man's preoccupations. The discovery of pain killers is one of the greatest achievements of the last two centuries in medicine, bringing relief to various medical conditions and facilitating complex surgical procedures. Similarly, emotional pain is dulled, reduced or controlled using various substances. Despite the numerous advantages of pain medicines, their use has gone from medical, to recreational and to pathological use as seen in various addictions.⁹

Various occupations attract the use of certain substances to ward off fatigue, treat or prevent pain or enhance performance e.g long distance drivers, heavy duty laborers, students, etc.¹⁰

Chronic pain is among the most common reasons adults seek medical care. Despite chronic pain's substantial impact on individuals' physical, emotional, and financial well-

being, the biologic underpinnings of chronic pain remain incompletely understood. The psychobiological processes explicating the increased risk of alcohol and substance misuse seen in subjects experiencing chronic stress and adversity and chronic pain are also not well understood. Individuals suffering from chronic pain find alleviation through prescription opioids as well as non-prescribed cannabis, alcohol, and other drugs to control pain.²⁷ In the systematic review by Morasco et al. among non-cancer patients with chronic pain, a prevalence of current substance use disorder (SUD) ranging from 3%–48% and a lifetime prevalence of any SUD ranging from 16%–74% were found.²⁸

Conversely, substance misuse also increases the experience of chronic stress. For example, 37% of patients in methadone maintenance and 24% of inpatients in drug treatment complain of severe chronic pain.^{27,29}

Opioid Abuse and Chronic pain

An estimated 60 million people used opioids in 2021, representing 1.2 per cent of the global adult population. Half of these live in South Asia or South-West Asia. Access to pharmaceutical opioids for pain management and palliative care vary considerably between LMIC and high-income countries.⁹

In the United states, Opioid use and abuse have risen markedly in the last few decades and have been estimated to consume 80% of the world's supply of opioids and 99% of the world's supply of hydrocodone.^{9,14}

The non-medical use of tramadol in North Africa, West Africa, the Middle East and South-West Asia, has been on the rise and continue to pose

significant health risks. In Africa, there have been signs of increases in the non-medical use of tramadol and its related harm in recent years.

Controlled drugs needed for palliative care and pain relief (pharmaceutical opioids), are denied to those who desperately need them, with too little access in many countries – mainly LMIC.⁹

While drug use problems may be global, they do not affect all the world equally. The vulnerable, the poor and the excluded continue to pay the highest price in our underdeveloped and underserved communities and villages.

According to the 2018 UNODC report “Drug use in Nigeria”, one in seven persons (aged 15–64 years) had used a drug in the past year. Drug abuse was reported to be common among undergraduates and secondary school students, youths, commercial bus drivers, farmers, and sex workers.^{10,11} Commonly abused drugs include cannabis, cocaine, amphetamine, heroin, diazepam, codeine, cough syrup and tramadol. Drug sources included pharmacies/patent medicine shops, open drug markets, drug hawkers, fellow drug abusers, friends, drug pushers and health workers. Reasons for drug use included: to increase physical performance, reduce stress and to derive pleasure. Poor socioeconomic factors and low educational background were the common risk factors associated with drug abuse.¹⁰

Mechanism of long-term potential for relapses

One of the most insidious features of opioid addiction is the tendency to relapse on the drug even weeks,

months, or years following abstinence. The mechanism for this type of relapse is still undergoing intense studies which suggest 3 distinct mechanisms for relapse: Stress; exposure to conditioned cues related to past drug use; a dose of the previously administered drug or a drug with similar properties.¹⁴

Evidence suggests that long-term administration of opioids can permanently alter the density of dendritic spines of certain neurons, and these permanent changes may contribute to long-lasting vulnerability to relapse.¹⁴

Opioid-induced hyperalgesia (OIH)

Hyperalgesia, defined as increased sensitivity to pain stimuli can follow chronic opioids use called Opioid-induced hyperalgesia (OIH). Allodynia however, is pain caused by ordinarily non-painful stimuli. Hyperalgesia is noted in parts of the body different from the site of the original pain complaint, and the descriptors of the pain change with some similarity to certain aspects of neuropathic pain, such as burning sensation. Unlike tolerance, OIH worsens with higher doses of opioids.^{14,18}

The pathophysiology of OIH is not well understood. A proposed mechanism is the activation of the NMDA receptor. This activation results in calcium influx, which in turn enhances the excitability of neurons, which facilitates further transmission of painful stimuli.¹⁸

Psychological Disorders among SCD patients

Several studies have elucidated on the increased risk for psychological disorders among people with SCD.

While some studies indicate high prevalence, some found low rates of psychological disorder. For example, in the study by Al Zahrani et al.³⁰ in a tertiary hospital in The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, they found the rate of depression and anxiety to be 36% and 29% respectively with a female preponderance, while the study in a teaching hospital in Ghana by Anim et al.³¹ found a rate of any psychological symptom among adult SCD patients to be 10% and no significant sex difference. Both studies used screening instruments to detect psychological disorders. To assess the reason for the high variability in the rate of psychological symptoms among adults with SCD, Doglioni et al.³² carried out a systematic review of literature and found differences in the study population, settings, screening and diagnostic instruments as well as study design as reasons for the differences in rates of psychological disorders. However, in the study by Raji et al. in Nigeria among 205 stable adult SCD patients attending out-patient clinic, they use the Mini International Neuropsychiatric Interview (MINI), which is a diagnostic instrument, and found the rate of depression to be 16.6%.³³

The Bethesda Sickle Cell Cohort Study by Wallen et al. found the rate of depression and sleep disturbance of 20.6% and 71.2% respectively using the Beck Depression Inventory and the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index to screen 328 subjects. Half of the those who screen positive for depression had suicidal ideation.²⁶

Management of Chronic pain

Current management of chronic pain irrespective of aetiology and setting is based on expert opinions and

policy/best practice guidelines and consensus by professional bodies; and this must take into consideration the multidimensional aspect of chronic pain especially when associated substance use disorder and mental disorders. This summary only considers the general principles thus:

Management of chronic pain must take a multi-disciplinary approach which may include pain management expert, behavioral psychologist, mental health specialists, physiotherapists, occupational therapist, and the primary managing physician depending on the primary diagnosis, comorbidity and setting. There could also be a spiritual dimension to how pain is perceived, interpreted and lived, which may then require spiritual guidance depending on the faith of the patient.

Clinicians must actively guard against medical gaslighting (also called medical invalidation), which is more likely to occur with chronic pain and in a setting of multiple somatic complaints. Medical gaslighting describes negative patient experiences of having their genuine clinical concerns inappropriately dismissed or invalidated by their attending physicians without proper medical evaluation, because of physician ignorance, implicit bias, or medical paternalism. It is usually not deliberate.³⁴

Chronic pain management should hence take care of the patient's religious and cultural background, educational level, patient's perceived cause of the pain, consequences of the pain in terms of work, relationships, leisure and burden of care.

When all these components are considered, it becomes glaring and worrisome, the wide gap between the ideal and what is obtainable on available treatment services in many Low- and Middle-Income Countries. Many pharmacotherapeutic options (such as longer acting opioid agonists, opioid partial agonists and antagonists etc) are either unavailable, highly restricted or beyond the reach of many patients in LMICs in addition to the few specialists available and lack of specialized centers.^{9,14,35} Other considerations will depend on the detected comorbidities such as depression, anxiety, sleep difficulty, sexual concerns and cognitive difficulties. Other non-pharmacological interventions include meditation, yoga, exercise, acupuncture, cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT), etc.

This observational case series was designed to answer the following research questions: What are the types and the pattern of substance misuse among SCD patients? What is the socio-demographic characteristics of adult SCD patients using substances? What are the risk factors for substance use disorder among SCD patients? and what is the comorbidity pattern among patients with SCD using substances? It is hoped that the answers to these questions will increase awareness among clinicians of the increasing risk of substance use disorders in SCD patients and the need for early recognition, treatment and prevention and also the need for a holistic and multidisciplinary approach towards management of pain crises among SCD patients.

Methodology:

This was a mixed method study involving both descriptive observational case series, as well as detailed qualitative clinical interview of participants using semi-structured clinical interview.

Study location: this was a private multi-specialist hospital, located in Makurdi, the Benue state capital in North-central Nigeria. The center is manned by various medical consultants who treat and receive referral cases for various medical conditions from the state and its neighbours.

Study population: these were adult patients diagnosed with sickle cell disease presenting to psychiatric section of the above private multi-specialist hospital, in North-central Nigeria. All participants had received at least two years' follow-up consultation.

Inclusion criteria: at least 18 years old; diagnosed with SCD, using substance(s) and consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion criteria: diagnoses of substance use disorder not met even if using substances for pain management.

Diagnoses of substance use disorders were made by the consultant psychiatrist based on the ICD 11 diagnostic criteria for substance use disorders.³⁶ Diagnosis of SCD had previously been established by the consultant haematologist using Hemoglobin Electrophoresis. Additional information were obtained from patients' case files as well as clinical interviews and use of a structured proforma.

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Ethics and scientific committee of the Federal University of Health Sciences Otukpo, Benue State.

Data Analysis

Data was analyzed using IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 25. Data was analyzed for descriptive statistics and triangulated with data from the qualitative interview.

Result

In all, 8 patient cases out of 11, met the inclusion criteria and recruited for the study. Three of the cases were excluded though the patients have been diagnosed with SCD and were attending the specialist psychiatric clinic, they did not meet the diagnostic criteria for substance use disorder (SUD). Mean age of participants 34.57 (SD± 5.79). Only one of the patients had SC genotype while the others had SS type. All the participants had at least a secondary level education, and most of them (87%) were single.

Types of substances used by patients include: opioids (pentazocine); stimulants (amphetamine); psychedelics (ketamine) and cannabis (table 2). Pentazocone was the commonest drug of abuse, followed by cannabis. Three of the 6 subjects who used pentazocine inject selves, and presented with varying degree of dirty wounds, ulcers, abscesses and ugly scars/swellings. Use of Ketamine was revealed by urine toxicology screening of one of the subjects (though use was denied by subject).

Table 3 shows the various reason clients gave for using substances. One of the patient insist that use of amphetamine relieves episodes of

priapism. Most of the clients admit to significantly reduced religious activities, had few or no friends to support, and their family believe they were using substances on purpose. All the clients have had at least two relapse episodes of SUD in the past 2 years following a period of abstinence. At least 62.5 % of the clients had comorbid SUD and MI (which included depression, anxiety, insomnia and aggressive tendencies).

Three of the clients only have partial insight concerning their SUD as they believe they are in control of use of the substance (cannabis) and that the substance use is not a problem. This is despite having continuous problems with family members, inability to keep a job and occasionally disruptive behaviour.

Two of the subjects had recurrent suicidal ideations for which they were treated with antidepressants.

Even though most of the clients believe they were using pentazocine for pain management, half (50%) of them were able the differentiate the feelings of craving from pain symptoms. One of the patient said use of pentazocine is preferred because of its rapid onset of action for pain management. All the subjects admit to being able to get their substances off the counter (pentazocine) without prescription, from friends and designated joints and dealers (cannabis and amphetamine).

Discussion

The use of psychotropics beyond medically prescribed boundaries is being increasingly recognized among persons with SCD. Even though current medical practice emphasize the need to abolish pain in all its

ramification, it can become tricky identifying the boundaries of rational use of analgesics for pain (especially the opioids) considering the pleasure and anxiolytic advantages they give. Unfortunately, most SCD patients abusing substances are not identified as they frequently deny or fail to admit substance use.

At least 5 of the clients using substances had co-morbid mental illness. This is similar to findings in other studies.^{6,7,26,30} The high

comorbidity is likely to reflect the fact that SCD is frequently associated with psychological distress either arising from the frequent pain crises, psychological and financial burnout by patients and their caregivers, or social withdrawal and being misunderstood by family and friends.³¹ Other psychosocial factors which may contribute involves being single, and low SES.

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Participants

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age: 34.57 ± 5.79		
Range: 23-34		
Gender:		
Male	3	37.5
Female	5	62.5
Occupation		
Unemployed	4	50
Employed	4	50
Educ. Level:		
Secondary	2	37.5
Tertiary	6	75.0
Marital Status		
Single	7	87.5
Married	1	12.5
SES		
Low	5	62.5
Middle	1	12.5
High	2	25.0
MI		
Yes	5	62.5
No	3	37.5

*MI = Mental illness; SES = Socioeconomic status

Table 2 Types and Pattern of Substances use Disorders

Substances	Abuse	Dependence
Opioids	-	6
Stimulants	-	1
Cannabis	4	1
Psychedelics	1	-
Total	5	8

Table 3 Reasons for Substance use

Reasons	N	%*
Pain management	5	62.5
Cravings	5	62.5
Withdrawal symptoms	5	62.5
Availability	5	62.5
Sleeplessness/sleepiness	2	25.0
Relaxing	3	37.5
Loss of appetite	1	12.5
To stay awake	1	12.5
Manage priapism	1	12.5

*total is greater than 100% due to multiple response

Table 4: Co-morbidities among SCD

Disorder	YES (%)
MI	5 (62.5)
SUD	8 (100.0)
BOTH	5 (62.5)

*MI: Mental Illness; SUD: Substance use disorder

Studies have shown associations between SCD with anxiety disorders, depression, insomnia, poor sexual performance, and impaired cognition.^{6,7,26,30-33} Studies have also shown the intricate relationship between depression and inflammatory processes, taking cognizance that the vaso-occlusive crises are usually accompanied by a cascade of the inflammatory process.³⁷

Use of Ketamine was revealed by urine toxicology screening of the subjects (and not orally admitted) and is likely to reflect the tendency for other drugs to be laced with other substances especially cannabis and alcohol to increase their potency and psychedelic experience. Studies in Nigeria among young persons reveal that polydrug use is the norm rather than the exception.⁹⁻¹¹

Only patients injecting selves had ulcers, dirty wounds and abscesses. This is because they lack the medical skills and knowledge on appropriate injecting techniques such as appropriate sites for injection, sterilization of injection site and repeated use of the same needle and syringe. They also inject into adipose and connective tissue, and other extra-vascular space.

All subjects using pentazocine were able to get it over the counter without a prescription, similar to findings in other studies.^{10,38} This again brings to the fore, the presence of unregulated chemists and pharmaceutical shops manned by quacks, poor supervision and monitoring of activities of medicine patent stores within the community.

Conclusion

Substance use disorders is a common occurrence among Sickle Cell Disease patients. This is however under-reported, poorly recognized and poorly treated. Mental health disorders are a frequent complications of the SCD trajectory, emphasizing the importance of a holistic multidisciplinary approach in the management of adults with sickle cell disease.

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